

PERMEABILITY PREDICTION IN POROUS MEDIA WITH COMPLEX 3D ARCHITECTURES IN A TRI-PERIODIC COMPUTATIONAL DOMAIN

W. R. Hwang¹, J. F. Wang^{1,2} and H. L. Liu¹

¹School of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, Research Center for Aircraft Parts Technology (ReCAPT), Gyeongsang National University, Jinju 660-701, South Korea

²School of Energy and Power Engineering, Jiangsu University, Zhenjiang 212-013, China

wrhwang@gnu.ac.kr; leo@gnu.ac.kr; wangjunfeng@ujs.edu.cn

SUMMARY

A 3D finite-element scheme combined with fictitious-domain/mortar-element method is presented to investigate the permeability of fibrous porous medium using a representative tri-periodic domain. The current scheme has been verified by comparison with existing literatures and employed to predict permeability of fibrous porous medium with various complicated 3D architecture.

Keywords: liquid composite molding, permeability, fictitious domain method

INTRODUCTION

The liquid composite molding (LCM) has been widely used in the aerospace, automotive and transportation industries, as an efficient process for manufacturing polymer composite products. The impregnation in the textile preform is generally modelled as the viscous flow through the porous media using Darcy's law that relates the fluid velocity to the applied pressure gradient:

$$\bar{v} = -\frac{K \Delta p}{\mu \Delta L} \quad (1)$$

where \bar{v} , K , μ , Δp and ΔL are the average velocity, the permeability, the fluid viscosity, the pressure difference and the length of the porous specimen in the flow direction, respectively. Darcy's law makes all the complicated interaction between the liquid and the fiber preform structure lumped into the permeability K . Accurate permeability is the most important parameter to successful process design. For this purpose, experimental techniques to determine the permeability have been developed in past decade [1-3]. However these measurements are known to be subject to a verity of local experimental parameter, in general, have no predictive capability. Therefore, a great deal of effort has been devoted to develop predictive models to understand the relationship between the microstructure and the macroscopic permeability. The works have so far been done described flow along and perpendicular to fibers reasonably well by their simplified 2D models [4-6], but face limitation in their ability to predict permeability in complex 3D geometries. The applications of various 3D performs to achieve the easy manufacturing

process and high mechanical property in today's industry prompt the study of permeability to more realistic 3D architecture.

In this work, a finite-element scheme combined with fictitious-domain/mortar-element method is presented to investigate the permeability of 3D geometry in a representative tri-periodic domain. The reliability of our scheme has been verified by comparison with existing literatures. The permeability to various 3D architectures has been presented.

MODELLING AND NUMERICAL METHODS

In modeling the fibrous porous media with complex architecture, we introduced representative tri-periodic domain concept such that a single unit problem with a relatively small number of fiber filaments or bundles may represent a large number of repeated structures. For example, the regular square packing fiber bed could be modeled by single fiber filament in a tri-periodic element as indicated in Fig.1. The Cartesian x and y coordinates are selected as parallel and normal to the fiber axis, the z direction obeys right-hand rule.

Figure 1. The regular (*left*) and the verification for the transverse permeability prediction, in comparison with existing literatures (*right*).

The governing equations of the three-dimensional Stokes flow are employed to describe the polymer flow slowly through fiber array.

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{0}, \quad \text{in } \Omega \setminus B \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0, \quad \text{in } \Omega \setminus B \quad (3)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = -p\mathbf{I} + 2\eta(\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}})\mathbf{D}, \quad \text{in } \Omega \setminus B \quad (4)$$

Eqs. (1)-(3) are for the momentum balance, the continuity, the constitutive relation, and the symbols \mathbf{u} , $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, p , \mathbf{I} , \mathbf{D} and η are the velocity, the stress, the pressure, the identity tensor, the rate-of-deformation tensor and the viscosity, respectively. The shear rate $\dot{\boldsymbol{\gamma}} = (2\mathbf{D} : \mathbf{D})^{1/2}$ is the second invariant of $2\mathbf{D}$ in the complex flow. The fluid attached on the fiber must be stationary:

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0} \quad \text{on } \partial B_i \quad (5).$$

In addition, the flow is driven by the pressure drop between inlet and outlet.

The 3D geometry of fiber filament is described by a number of uniform distributed collocation points on its surface only which is a fictitious domain method similar to the distributed Lagrangian multipliers (DLM) method. With these techniques, the hydrodynamic interaction can be treated implicitly via a combined weak formulation in our finite-element scheme, thus, the permeability tensor of 3D architecture can be calculated readily with a relative lower computational cost.

In order to combine the tri-periodic boundary condition with our current scheme, the continuity of the velocity field and the force balance need to be satisfied across the domain boundary. These conditions can be written as Eqs. (6)-(8) in each directions:

$$\mathbf{u}(0, y, z) = \mathbf{u}(L, y, z) \quad y \in [0, W] \quad z \in [0, H] \quad (6a)$$

$$\mathbf{t}(0, y, z) = -\mathbf{t}(L, y, z) \quad y \in [0, W] \quad z \in [0, H] \quad (6b)$$

$$\mathbf{u}(x, 0, z) = \mathbf{u}(x, W, z) \quad x \in [0, L] \quad z \in [0, H] \quad (7a)$$

$$\mathbf{t}(x, 0, z) = -\mathbf{t}(x, W, z) \quad x \in [0, L] \quad z \in [0, H] \quad (7b)$$

$$\mathbf{u}(x, y, 0) = \mathbf{u}(x, y, H) \quad x \in [0, L] \quad y \in [0, W] \quad (8a)$$

$$\mathbf{t}(x, y, 0) = -\mathbf{t}(x, y, H) \quad x \in [0, L] \quad y \in [0, W] \quad (8b)$$

RESULTS AND DISSCUSSIONS

To examine the feasibility and reliability of the present scheme, the single fiber problem as indicated in Fig. 2 is tested. The fiber could be located either in the centre or corners split in y-z plane along the x direction to present the regular square packing fiber bed according to our tri-periodic scheme. The fiber radius r is 0.1 and the size of domain is $1 \times 1 \times 0.2$. Throughout the study, the fluid viscosity and pressure gradient both have been chosen at 1.

Figure 2. A single fiber in a tri-periodic domain, located in the centre (*left*) or in corner split (*right*), represents the regular square packing fiber bed.

Furthermore, we compared shear rate distribution along the diagonal in y-z plane ($x = 0$) for both centre located and corner split fiber configurations. The quintiles of the shear rate in corresponding positions of two cases are exactly identical which verify the excellent satisfactory of tri-periodic boundary condition.

Figure 3. The quantitative comparison of the shear rate distribution in y direction along the diagonal. The coordinate in split fiber is adjusted for comparison.

The normalized transverse permeability of regular square packing structure calculated for various values of fiber volume fraction by our scheme, together with the predicted values by Gebart [5] and our previous 2D work, Wang and Hwang [7], were plotted on Fig.4 (left) for comparison. And we also showed the longitudinal permeability prediction in compared with results of Chen and Papathanasiou [6]. Our predictions of transverse permeability agree well with literature, while have small deviation of longitudinal permeability from conventional method.

Figure 4. The predictions of transverse (*left*) and longitudinal (*right*) normalized permeability (K / r^2) for regular square packing fiber bed in the comparison with literatures: Gebart [5], Wang and Hwang [7] and Chen and Papathanasiou [6].

Then we construct a model with two-crossed fiber to investigate the flow behaviour and permeability. Two fibers with uniform radius locate orthogonally in a tri-periodic

domain at the size of $1 \times 1 \times 2$ as shown in Fig.3. As the volume fraction, ϕ_f , decreased from 0.6 in Fig. 5 (a) to 0.35 in Fig. 5 (b), we may observe the high shear rate region appeared nearby the fiber surface. Furthermore, the normalized permeability K'_{yy} / r^2 calculated under various volume fraction of current model is in-between the transverse and longitudinal values from verification part.

Figure 5. The velocity field and shear rate distribution in two crossed fibers model: (a) $\phi_f = 0.6$ ($r = 0.437$), (b) $\phi_f = 0.35$ ($r = 0.3338$)

Figure 6. The normalized permeability K / r^2 of two-crossed fibers compare with transverse and longitudinal of single fiber by our 3D code.

Three fibers with uniform radius, $r = 0.19$, in a tri-periodic representative cell at size $1 \times 1 \times 1$ is presented in Fig. 7 along with the shear rate distribution and velocity field on different plane, which could represent a complicated fabric architecture. The high shear rate region hardly could be noticed, and flow field on the plane as indicated in Fig.7 (b) is complex. Two main flows, along with the y axis and z axis respectively, could be observed

Figure 7. The velocity field and shear rate distribution on different planes in crossed fiber filaments model

Finally, we present a porous structure with 7 spheres at different radius in a unit tri-periodic domain. The flow seems more complex from the velocity and shear rate distributions than in fibrous porous media.

Figure 7. The porous media with sphere along with velocity field and shear rate distribution on different planes.

CONCUSION

The current 3D finite-element scheme combined with fictitious-domain/mortar-element method demonstrated the feasibility of our scheme in predicting the permeability in fibrous porous media with complex architectures. Various complicated 3D architectures would be modelled to investigate the permeability which is valuable to industry applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by Korea Research Foundation Grant of Korean Government (KRF-2008-005-J01001) and by the BK 21 Project.

References

1. Baichen L, Bickerton S, Advani S. G., Modelling and simulation of resin transfer molding (RTM) – Gate control, venting and dry spot prediction. *Composites Part A* 1996; 27:135–41.
2. Weitzenböck J. R., Shenoit R. A. and Wilson P. A. Radial flow permeability measurement. Part A: Theory. *Composites Part A* 1999; 30: 781-796.
3. Hoes K, Dinescu D, Sol H. New set-up for measurement of permeability properties of fibrous reinforcements for RTM. *Composites Part A* 2002; 33: 959–969.
4. Brusckke M. V., Advani S. G., Flow of generalized Newtonian fluids across a periodic array of cylinders, *Journal of Rheology* 1993; 37: 479-498.
5. Gebart B. R., Permeability of Unidirectional Reinforcements for RTM. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 1992; 26:1100-1133.
6. Chen X. and Papathanasiou T.D., Micro-scale modelling of axial flow through unidirectional disordered fiber arrays, *Composites Science and Technology* 2007; 67: 1286-1293
7. Wang J. F. and Hwang W. R., Permeability prediction of fibrous porous media in a bi-periodic domain, *Journal of Composite Materials* 2008; 42: 909-929